

GLASS CEILING IN PRIVATE SECTOR FOR WOMEN EMPLOYEE

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Abstract

This research address different concerns of Woman class ceiling in workplace and its impact on women employee while working in the organization. Gender discrimination in workforce was measured through independent samples-t test. The analysis shows that females were discriminated more than males in private organizations. Thus the findings show that females are discriminated more than males in private sector than in public sector. The impact of gender discrimination on satisfaction & motivation, commitment & enthusiasm and stress level was assessed through Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient. The results show that gender discrimination decreases satisfaction & motivation and commitment & enthusiasm level of employees, and increases the stress level in the employees.

Keywords : Gender discrimination, Workforce, Satisfaction & Motivation, Commitment & Enthusiasm, Stress Level.

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Introduction

- The pandemic has had a disproportionate impact on women's economic participation.
- Gender equality cannot be achieved without support from the private sector.
- A new survey shows strong worldwide belief that the private sector must lead on gender initiatives.

Women earn, on average, 24 percent less than men. In companies, women hold very few percent of CEO positions and take hardly find a position in board seats. Yet research suggests that increasing the proportion of women on boards of directors is linked to better financial results and higher levels of corporate philanthropy.

Across India, young women and men entering the labour force today have nearly the same level of educational qualifications. But they often don't face equal opportunities at work place.

women carry a uneven burden of unpaid work – for example, caring for young, elderly, sick and/or disabled family members; and in obtaining and preparing food. These tasks not only demand substantial time and energy but also can prevent women from fulfilling their aspirations and deprive economies of women's full talents and contributions.

Currant Fact:

Globally, on average, the public sector has a higher share of female employees than the formal private sector, with around 41% of women working in the former and 38% in the latter. Although in most countries women represent a smaller share of employment than men in both the public and private sectors, the public sector seems to do a little better in achieving gender parity

The gender pay gap is ten percentage points lower in the public sector than the formal private sector.

While women are well represented in the public sector, they are underrepresented at the “top” Women occupy less than 30% of “senior official” positions in the public sector, while representing around 50% of clerical positions. Achieving greater gender parity will require policies aimed not just at improving women’s representation at the ‘top’, but at addressing occupational segregation more

generally.

Women as a share of public employees, by occupation. Source: WWBI data

Steps that private sector can push for gender equality:

Women’s equality in the workplace is a critical component of gender equality and sustainable development. It would not only improve the prospects of women, but would also have a profound impact on the development of the country.

As part of its efforts to drive inclusive development and advance gender equality, we should foster public-private partnerships aimed at closing gender gaps in the workplace. These practices may helpin public and private sector to meet high standards for gender equality in their workplaces. By addressing gender disparities in the workplace and establishing environments where women’s work and contributions are valued, companies have experienced benefits such as greater efficiency, improved staff performance, increased employee commitment to the company, and improved recruitment – not to mention an enhanced public image.

The importance of private sector engagement in advancing gender equality in the workplace cannot be overstated. How business does business, and to what degree it ensures that men and women can contribute and benefit equally, will have a huge impact on whether sustainable development is

achieved. By making gender equality central to its business practices, the private sector can be a driver of progress that benefits all.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, the World Economic Forum estimated that it would take almost 100 years to close the global gender gap. Today, more than a year since the emergence of COVID-19 and days before the Generation Equality Forum (GEF), hard-won gains for gender equality are at risk of rollback due to the disproportionate burden that girls and women have experienced throughout the pandemic.

In addition to concerning increases in gender-based violence and disruptions in access to sexual and reproductive health services, the pandemic's global economic crisis is swiftly altering women's economic participation. Before the pandemic, experts stated that narrowing the global gender gap in work made business sense, and would boost global GDP growth. A reversal of progress on gender equality is economically costly. Companies cannot afford to ignore that women's jobs have been 1.8 times more vulnerable to this crisis than men's jobs largely because of existing gender inequalities. All around the world, women are experiencing higher rates of unemployment due to job losses or leaving work to manage childcare.

REFERENCE

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